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Assessment Of The Impact Of Petroleum Gas Flare On Three Crop Plants At Amukpe-Sapele Community, Delta State Nigeria

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ABSTRACT

Gas flaring is an important combustion mechanisms in the burning of surplus undesirable fluids (gas in particular) that are released during the ordinary or unexpected over-pressuring process in several industrial, activities specifically in the petroleum resource industries. It is one of the main sources of green house gas emissions which causes climate change. In addition to the generation of noise and heat, it makes a considerable areas unsuitable and as a result causes harmful consequences to the entire biosphere and also result in economic losses. This study assesses the impact of petroleum gas flaring on yam, maize and cassava, crops-Gas flaring was observed to have effect on crop growth, yield, air, water and on soil characteristics. Result shoed significant negative impacts on crop performance which include reduced growth rate, yields and altered soil fertility. Thus study also highlighted the Need for alleviation initiatives to reduce the adverse effects of gas flaring on agricultural areas and food security in the region and Nigeria in general.

Keywords: Gas flaring, crop plants, petroleum, combustion mechanisms, Assessment, Amukpe-Sapele, climate change, Green house gases.

INTRODUCTION

Evidence abound that altered weather patterns and climate change are largely responsible for poor plant growth and development with tendency of threat to species extinction and food insecurity. Pollution on the environment can occur due to natural as well as anthropogenic causes.

The Central Pollution Board has identified seventeen (17) categories of heavily polluting industries in the world. These are thermal power plants, distilleries, iron and steel industries, pulp and paper industries, oil refineries, petrol chemical industries, pesticides, zinc, copper and aluminum industries, drugs and pharmaceuticals, dye and dye intermediates, cement, sugar factories (anonymous 1998). In this study area, the oil and gas industry is the source of these emissions as a result of gas flaring. This does not only reduce the quality of air we breathe, but also on the hydro geological cycle that support Irrigation and off – season farming. Greenhouse gases cause a rise in atmospheric temperature which is detrimental to plant physiological processes.

The assessment of this man-made problem is desirable in an attempt to facilitate mitigation of same and also to ameliorate soil infertility due to cumulative effects of leaching or nutrient drain.

Gas Flaring

Crude oil is a mixture of liquids and gases, mostly hydrocarbons and brought to the surface through the process of drilling. (Ake 1979), cited by Nwaugo, Ouyeagba & Nwachukwu (2006). While the removal of the associated substances which includes inorganic matters, water and gasses with crude oil does not change its state (Nwaugo et al; 2006).

Gas flaring is mainly used to dispose of the associated gases with crude oil to enhance its economic values (Bassey, 2008). There are arguments that the exact scientific impact of gas flaring on health and safety, environment and stakeholders has not been established conclusively (Bassey 2008). Elvidge, et al; 2009). But findings have suggested that there are environmental, health and safety concerns relating to gas flaring not just in Nigeria but the world all over especially in view of climate change. (Oluwasoye et al; 2016).

Globally, the rate of scale accounted from crude oil extraction through natural gas flaring is measured as 16%, 11% and 10% to Nigeria, Russia and Iran respectively, which world Bank set year 2030 as the stoppage deadline for gas flaring gaseous substances especially among the three major countries (Word Bank, 2015). In addition, the foreign dominance by International Oil Companies (IOCs) with 94% against 6% indigenous participation (Eboh, 2015); General Electric Energy, 2010) has Majorly contributed to the different environmental laws in Nigeria (Mahler, 2010). Besides, natural gaseous flaring substance has been estimated to be measured for almost 410billion standardized cubic feet in the 2013 fiscal year, which loss estimation is quoted as 272.8billion naira as reported by the Nigeria National Petroleum Corporation (Eboh, 2015).

However, the definition of gas flaring which states that it is an anthropogenic activity that involves the discharge of unwanted radiations from greenhouse gases (GHGs) that leads to heating, imbalance earth, uncertain climate change conditions and environmental disasters, additionally, natural gas flaring is an emission of a noxious mixture, which is allowed by the benzene but it is harmful to human beings, lower animals, green plants and the whole geographical earth (World Bank, 1995).

Effects of Gas Flaring

The environmental disasters and problems in the Niger Delta region of Nigeria has been documented in several studies. Some examples are in studies carried out by (Mafimisebi, 2013, Nkwunowu & Mafimisebi, 2013; Mafimisebi & Nkwunowu, 2014; 2015; Mafimisebi, & Thorne, 2015; 2016). However, on particular concern, evidence to wasteful oil and gas operations, gas flaring is a distinctive feature of the Niger Delta Landscape. Most of these flares are on twenty –four (24) hours daily and some have been on for over fifty (50) years in the region. The communities within these flare areas are usually deprived of even the comfort of night's natural darkness. Though it has not been conclusively assessed. The impact of gas faring on the local ecology and climate change as well as people's health and property is evident. The extremely high levels of carbon dioxide and Methane gases that are released to the atmosphere also have impact on the climate patterns beyond the local level (Steiner, 2010). It has been revealed that gas faring usually lead to Ozone Layer depletion, climate change, global warming, acid rain and rise in sea level. For example, acid rain is a direct result of gas flaring in the Niger Delta region. However, the main issues for awareness include;

a. Climate change: The flaring of gas releases green house gases like carbon dioxide and methane into the atmosphere. Of these two green house gases, Methane is more harmful than carbon dioxide (Steiner, 2010, Mafinisebi & Nkwunowu, 2014).

Typically, climate change impacts are more pronounced on low-lying coastal areas like the Niger – Delta region. They are prone to freak weather events, flooding and coastal erosion and are the first to be affected by rise in the sea level (Bassey, 2008). Because of rise in temperature, climate charge favours proliferation of pests and spread of diseases. They also affect Agricultural productivity seriously.

b. Ozone layer Depletion: Ozone is formed naturally in the upper atmosphere when oxygen Molecules are struck by ultra – violet light from the sun. Ozone absorbs ultra – violet (UV) rays and is continually

being broken into oxygen and recreated in natural equilibrium. Ozone also act as a green house gas. The chlorofluorocarbons can breakdown ozone. CFCs contains atoms, these can attach themselves to the oxygen atoms in ozone, thereby forming oxygen and chlorine-monoxide. One chlorine atom can breakdown 100,000 molecules of ozone. As the concentration of ozone falls, so does the temperature of the atmosphere. This leads to the formation of ice clouds which greatly speed up the ozone degradation process by providing a surface for reactions to take place which allow chlorine atoms to be separated from their constituent molecules, and thus become available for ozone destruction. (Nishet 1991).

c. Global warming: The long – term rise in Earth’s average surface temperature due to human activities, primarily due to the emission of green house gases, such as Methane (CH₄) and carbon dioxide (CO₂) is referred to as global warming.

The greenhouse affect refers to the phenomenon where by carbondioxide and other gases trap long wave infra-red radiation (heat) in the atmosphere thereby making the earth warm (Nkwunowu & Mafimisebi, 2013). It is a complete natural phenomenon, without global warming, the average temperature on the earth would be 33oC lower than at present. The infra-red emission by the earth can be tapped by atmospheric carbondioxide (CO₂), Nitrous oxide (NO₂) Chlorofluorocarbons (CFCs), Methane (CH₄), ozone (O₃) and other gases. The concentration of these greenhouse gases (GHGs) in the atmosphere reduces the re-radiation on heat into space. The operation on this mechanism, has become a pollution problem because of the rate at which anthropogenic emissions of infra-red trapping gases have increased, thereby creating a larger stock in the atmosphere. The major sources of CO₂ are the burning of fossil fuels like oil, coal and gas; CO₂ is also produced naturally by the decay of organic matters (Oluwasoye & Odinaka, 2016). The concentration of CO₂ in the upper atmosphere has risen from roughly 280 parts per million (ppm) in 1880 to 355ppm today (IPCC, 1992 as reported by Oluwasoye & Odinaka, 2016).

The major reason for this increase is the combustion of fossil fuels. The major sources of NO₂ in the atmosphere are the production of fertilizers and combustion of fossil fuels. CFCs are produced as propellant refrigerants and foam expanders and are used in air conditioning systems. Methane (CH₄) is produced from sewage treatment, life stock waste and land fill sites. The four major greenhouse gases vary in terms of their lifetime in the atmosphere before they are broken donor (CO₂: 50yrs; N₂O: 150yrs; CFCs: 75 -110yrs and Methane (CH₄) 9 – 13yrs (IPCC, 1992). They also vary in terms of “radioactive forcing”.

Global gas flaring is estimated to be more than 144BCM in 2021 (World Bank, 2022). Egypt contributed 1.45% of this amount (World Bank, 2022). Nowadays, the world is confronting global warming as one of its fundamental issues and this problem can be caused by a rise in CO₂, CH₄ and other greenhouse gases (GHGs) outflow within the atmosphere.

CO₂ is the main greenhouse gas that accounts for approximately three quarters of emissions. Climate change is the term used by researchers to describe the complex changes caused by green house gas concentration that impacts our planets, climate and weather frameworks. Climate change involves rising average temperatures which is known as global warming, extraordinary meteorological Phenomena, displacement on wild-life populations and habitats, higher seas and various other impacts (Singh, 2021).

In recent years, biodiversity (food crops inclusive) has gained increasing focus as an urgent and systematic environmental risk on global food security. Weather and climate change increases the incidence of pests and diseases that causes huge loss in crop production. It also reduces soil fertility, promote salinity and deterioration of immigration water quality. The increase in average temperature during growing season typically causes plants to use more energy for respiration to support their growth (FAO 2016). Researchers have explored the regulatory frameworks and policies governing gas flaring globally. These studies often analyze the effectiveness of existing regulations, propose improvements and examine the economic implications of compliance with flaring regulation (Okoro & Odo, 2014). Scholars have investigated various technological solutions to reduce or eliminate gas flaring activities. This includes the utilization of associated gas for power generation, the implementation of gas flare recovery systems and the development innovative flare minimization technologies (Nwaogazie et al; 2019).

Economic studies have examined the costs and benefits associated with gas flaring. These analyses often consider the financial implications of flaring reduction strategies, potentials for monetizing flared gas and the overall economic impacts on the oil and gas industry and local economies (Singer et al; 2020). Research has been conducted on specific regions and countries where gas flaring is prevalent. These case studies provide insights into the local context, challenges and opportunities for addressing gas flaring and offer valuable lessons for policy makers and industry stakeholders (Akinboye et al; 2021). Moreso, some studies have focused on the impacts of gas flaring on nearby communities and the social implications of living in areas close to flaring sites.

Researchers have explored the health risk associated with exposure to flaring emissions and the social justice aspects of environmental pollution from flaring activities. Temperature rise, which is a consequence of weather and climate change can take many forms. Crops are more sensitive to high temperature at the reproductive stages (FAO, IFADWFP, WHO, UNICEF, 2017). Plant responses to each type of temperature alternation and or rise is specie – specific (Adichi & Oluka, 2018; Ayinde et al; 2020). Weather and climate changes in Nigeria has induced drought and flooding of farmlands. Rising temperature increases soil aridity and increases water loss (evapo –transpiration) among others (Onuoha & Ezirin 2010; Idumah et al; 2016)

Problem Statement/Justification

Industrialization and economic prosperity are desirable, but must be reconciled with sustainable development objectives which are the ultimate goals of the United Nations Organizations (UNO). There must be a balance in order to prevent negative shift that comes with catastrophic consequences. Amukpe – Sapele is a home to oil mineral exploration and processing. These activities have been identified as the major source of the green house gases (GHGs) implicated in atmospheric temperature rise and acid rain. This study will reveal the Severity of the impacts these pollutants have on crop plants and the economic prosperity of the people. This study has also generated data and information to enrich existing pool of knowledge required to advise or enlighten farmers, industrial concerns as well as assist donor and interventionist organizations.

Objectives Of The Study

To identify and document the effects of gas flaring on the three plant species under investigation (Cassava, Maize and Yam).

To identify and document the factors that alter weather conditions in the short term and climate change in the long run.

Research Questions

Does greenhouse gases have any effect on the crops under investigation (Cassava, Maize and Yam)

Does gas flaring alter weather conditions in the short term and climate change in the long term.

METHODOLOGY

i. Study Area:

Amukpe is one of the adjoining communities to Sapele and part of Sapele Local Government Area in Delta Central Senatorial district. It is bordered by Ethiope West Local Government Area, Okpe Local Government Area and Warri North and South Local Government Areas respectively.

Amukpe – Sapele is easily identified by its continuous gas flare. The primary occupation of the people is farming and trading. The map below shows the stud area.

Figure I: Map of Sapele Local Government Area showing the location of Amukpe

In the study area, distances of 100m, 500m and 1000m were taken from the flaring point and samples of leaves stems and soils, were collected. Acid rain samples were also collected at the various distances. Atmospheric temperatures measurements were carried out weekly.

The leaves and stems of cassava (*Manihot esculent*), yam (*Discorea sp*) and maize (*Zea mays*) were collected at the various distances mentioned above. The parameters that were measured includes surface area of their leaves, plant height, size of yam and cassava tubers, and evidence of chlorosis and leaf texture. However, for comparative analysis, control was carried out in prestime locations.

Determination of Different Parameters

The leaf area: The leaf area of the yam and cassava were determined by tracing the outlines of the leaves on graph papers graduated in centimeters. While a leaf is being taken, the remaining ones were kept in close Petri dishes. This was to reduce the rate of desiccation that would affect leaf area measurement.

For the maize leaves the leaf areas was measured using a measuring tape. The leaf length was taken by measuring the leaf from the tip of the origin, while the breadth was taken by measuring the broadest portion of the leaf. The leaf area was obtained by multiplying the length by the breadth.

Chlorophyll Content Determination: One gram of fresh leaves was harvest from the different distances. They were blended and 10% of 70% acetone was added. The solutions were extracted using filter paper; the filtrates were placed in a spectrophotometer. The reading were taken at the wave length of 652W. This result is shown in table 19.

Fresh Weight Determination: The mean fresh weight of the leaves from the various samples were carefully determined using the metler electric weighing balance. The leaves, stems, roots and tubers were carefully separated; and the fresh weights were recorded. This is shown in table 6 below.

Dry weight Determination: The dry weight of the stems, leaves, roots and tubers of the various samples were determined. They were kept in the oven at a temperature of 105oC till a constant weight was obtained. These results are shown in table 7.

Leaf texture Determination: In other to determine the leaf texture of the crops under investigation, the leaves of the various crop plants were physically touch to have a feel of the presence of features like scales, hairs or glands. Tactile examination was also carried out on the various leaves. It was observed that the closer the leaves to the gas flaring point the more the concentration of hairs, scales and glands. It was also observed that the length and density of the various hairs present were also determined by the nearness to the flaring point. Moreover, in the control plants, there were also hairs, scales or gland on the surface of the leaves, but the concentrations were minimal. It therefore implied that the presence of high concentration of hairs on the surface of the plants closer to the flaring point may be taken as an adaptive

measure developed by the crops to fight against the effect of the various emissions as a result of the gas flaring.

The leaves closest to the flaring point were observed to be much more hairy and rough in comparison to those leaves from the control. The highest degree of the presence of hairs were found in leaves of plants 100m away from the flaring point followed by those in the distance 500m, then very few in those planted in 1000m away. For those in the control area, there were hairs, but not as much as in those ones in 100m, 500m and 1000m away from the point of the gas flaring.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Impact Assessment on soil, water and air quality

Table 1: Air Quality Assessment

Parameters (Mmol/s)	100m	500m	1000m	FEPA Standard (mmol/l)
CO	20.00 ± 0.010	15.00 ± 0.012	12.00 ± 0.18	10.00
NO ₂	0.50 ± 0.05	0.50 ± 0.02	0.40 ± 0.01	0.04 – 0.06
SO ₂	0.40 ± 0.005	0.40 ± 0.012	0.30 ± 0.009	0.01
CH ₄	0.50 ± 0.009	0.50 ± 0.009	0.40 ± 0.012	10.00
Particulates	1.60 ± 0.015	1.50 ± 0.012	1.30 ± 0.012	0.10

(CO, NO₂, SO₂, CH₄ and Particulates) from Amukpe – Sapele gas flaring site were above the WHO/FEPA Standard limit for normal environment, and they were higher when compared to values for communities that are very far from the flaring point. The mean value of all the air quality indices decreased as the distance from the flaring point increases, this indicating that gas diffusion decreases within increasing distance. This result corroborates the work of Njoku, et al; 2017 as cited by Oluwasoye & Odinaka in 2022.

From the above table 2, the mean values of PH of Soil in the three distances revealed that the samples from 100m distance is more acidic followed by 500m and then 1000m from the flaring point. High soil acidity creates chemical and biological conditions which may be harmful to plants and soil microorganisms. One of such conditions is the reduction in the ability of plants to absorb cations (Nagaraju et al; 2007). The higher the acidic nature of the soil, the higher the concentrations of Sulphur dioxide and Particulates from the gas flared into the atmosphere which is washed back to the soil as acid rain. This observation agrees with the reports of Nwaugo et al; 2006 as reported by Oluwasoye and Odinaka 2016 who opined that gas flaring increase soil acidity. This observation is also attributed to the high pollution level due to gas flaring, however the value of both NO₂ and SO₂ are below World Health Organization (WHO) Standard in 1987 and (FEPA) in 1991 soil standards.

The physiochemical parameters of the water samples from the three distances in shown in table 2 above. The PH of the samples ranged from 5.20 to 7.20. The Institute of Public Analysis of Nigeria (IPAN) reported that the PH of water is one of the most important water parameters. An optimum PH range is very important for clarification of portable water, while a range outside the acceptable standard could lead to objectionable taste.

In 2019, Abuchaogu et al studied the effects of gas flaring on surface water in Mkpanak community in Akwa Ibom state, Nigeria. The analysis was carried out using the standard methods of the American society for Testing and Materials (ASTM1999) and American Public Health Association (APHA) in 1998. The laboratory analysis carried out on the collected samples (gas flaring point and non-gas flaring point) includes the physical, chemical (including heavy metals analysis) and microbiological parameters. The physical parameters analyzed were Temperature, colour, transparency, Turbidity and Odour. The

chemical parameters checked were PH, Electrical conductivity (EC), Total Dissolved Solids (TDS), Salinity as in chlorine level (Cl⁻), Dissolved Oxygen (OD), Oxides of Nitrogen, Sulphur, Phosphorus, Potassium (K) and Sodium ions (Na⁺) adopting standard procedures. Digestion process was carried out using fume cupboard coupled with Atomic Absorption spectrometer (ASS. Model Unicam SOLAAR 969) appropriately to analyze the possibility of the presence of heavy metals.

Comparison of the average water sample in the study area with the average water sample from the control area, World Health Standard 2008 and Nigeria Standard for Drinking water quality for the purpose of identifying and validating if the results of the samples analyzed fall within the two standards.

Table 2: Values of water physiochemical parameters as compared with WHO/FEPA.

Physiochemical parameters (mg/l)	100m	500m	1000m	WHO/FEPA standards
pH	5.20	6.58	7.20	6.50 – 8.50
Total hardness	192. ± 1.20	40.00 ± 1.40	36.0 ± 2.10	- 0.50
Calcium hardness	160.00 ± 1.30	12.00 ± 1.25	11.00 ± 0.50	No limit
Total solid	800.00 ±10.00	70.00 ± 2.22	65.01 ± 1.60	No limit
Chloride	56.74 ± 2.50	1.28 ± 0.03	1.10 ± 0.001	250
Total dissolved solid	600 ± 5.20	66.00 ± 1.30	55.00 ± 1.10	100 – 1000
Total suspended solid	200.00 ±2.50	150.00 ± 1.45	100.00 ±1.25	No limit
Alkalinity	73.75 ± 3.25	64.00 ± 2.85	42.00 ± 1.40	No limit
Sulphate	12.00 ± 1.22	10.10 ± 0.56	9.41 ± 0.30	250 – 500
Phosphate	0.12 ± 0.06	0.08 ± 0.01	0.04 ± 0.001	< 5.0
Nitrate	8.00 ± 0.002	2.00 ± 0.01		10

Table 3: Moisture content, PH and Temperature of the various soil samples

Distance from flare point	A			B			C		
	PH	T (oc)	MC%	PH	T (oc)	MC%	PH	T (oc)	MC%
100m	4.20	60	18	4.00	55.00	15.00	4.20	50.00	18.00
500m	5.00	46.00	26.00	5.10	4.00	21.00	5.20	41.00	25.00
1000m	6.10	33.00	35.00	6.30	32.00	35.00	6.30	31.00	34.00
Control	6.60	45.00	45.00	6.70	29.00	41.00	6.60	30.00	40.00

The result obtained from the environmental analysis indicated that the PH of rainwater (<5.60) were not within regulation limit for the gas flaring location point. Samples of rainwater collected during the dry season were more acidic than those collected during the rainy season, this is due to the fact that acids were formed more in the atmosphere in the dry season and they are more likely to be diluted in rainy season. Moreso, the average of soil temperature (54.00oC and 42.00oC) as against 30.00oC, Soil PH of (4.10 – 5.10) as against 6.70 and the low soil moisture content of (17.00% - 23.00%) as against 40.00% for the (100m and 500m) and the control.

The results therefore showed that gas flaring is responsible for the contamination of the environment which then affected the growth and development of plants in the various distances from the flaring point thereby affecting agricultural activities.

Table 4: Effect of gas flaring on the stem height in (*Zea mays*) maize

Distance from flaring point	Mean stem height (cm ²)
100m	90.00 ± 9.00
500m	105.00 ± 10.00
1000m	120.00 ± 12.00
Control	180.00 ± 18.00

Values are means of 5 replicates ± S.E.

From the table 4 above, it showed that as the distance increases from the flaring point there was progressive increase in the stem height in *Zea mays* which means that there is significant effect on the plants by the emissions. In the control, average stem height of 120.00cm² was recorded.

Table 5: Effect of gas flaring on leaf production in (*Zea mays*) Maize

Distance from flaring point	Mean number of leaf/plant
100m	15.60 ± 3.01
500m	19.20 ± 1.59
1000m	26.60 ± 3.01
Control	38.41 ± 5.02

Values are means of 5 replicate ± standard error

Table 6: Effects of gas flaring on the fresh weight of leaves, stems and roots of maize (*Zea mays*).

Distance from flaring point	Fresh weight (g)		
	Leaf	Stem	Root
100m	2.92 ± 0.58	4.42 ± 0.88	6.32 ± 1.26
500m	3.40 ± 0.68	6.58 ± 1.32	7.48 ± 1.50
1000m	5.32 ± 1.00	8.42 ± 1.68	10.64 ± 2.13
Control	9.40 ± 1.88	10.28 ± 2.85	12.46 ± 2.50

Values are means of 5 replicates (±) standard error.

Table 7: Effects of gas flaring on the dry weight of leaves stems & root of (*Zea mays*) maize.

Distance from flaring point	Dry weight (g)		
	Leaf	Stem	Root
100m	1.82 ± 0.36	3.18 ± 0.64	4.01 ± 0.80
500m	2.98 ± 0.60	5.36 ± 1.07	6.12 ± 1.22
1000m	4.36 ± 0.87	7.48 ± 1.50	8.10 ± 1.62
Control	7.26 ± 1.45	8.24 ± 1.65	10.44 ± 2.09

Values are means of 5 replicates (±) standard error

Table 8: Effects of gas flaring on leaf area development of (*Zea Mays*) Maize

Distance from flaring point	Leaf area (cm ²)
100m	200.60 ± 40.12
500m	220.89 ± 44.18
1000m	250.64 ± 50.13
Control	290.82 ± 58.16

Values are means of 5 replicates (±) standard error

Table 9: Effects of gas flaring on leaf area development in cassava (*Mainhot esculenta*)

Distance from flaring point	Leaf area (cm ²)
100m	82.50 ± 14.50
500m	90.51 ± 17.74
1000m	100.12 ± 17.37
Control	108.62 ± 18.38

Table 10: Effects of gas flaring on Stem height in cassava (*mainhot esculenta*)

Distance from flaring point	Mean stem height (cm ²)
100m	30.38 ± 6.08
500m	42.11 ± 8.42
1000m	60.35 ± 12.07
Control	150.21 ± 3.04

Values are means of five replicates (±) standard error

Table 11: Effects of gas flaring on leaf production in cassava (*Mainhot esculenta*)

Distance from flaring point	Mean numbers of leaf/plant
100m	10.45 ± 2.09
500m	19.68 ± 3.94
1000m	28.45 ± 5.69
Control	40.25 ± 8.05

Values are mean of 5 replicates (±) standard error

Table 12: Effects of gas flaring on the fresh weight of the leaves of cassava (*Manihot esculenta*)

Distance from flaring point	Fresh weight (g)		
	Leaf	Stem	Root
100m	2.88 ± 0.58	6.42 ± 1.28	3.89 ± 0.78
500m	3.96 ± 0.80	8.06 ± 1.61	6.42 ± 1.28
1000m	4.58 ± 0.92	10.41 ± 2.08	8.96 ± 1.80
Control	8.46 ± 1.70	15.248 ± 3.06	10.03 ± 2.01

Table 13: Effects of gas flaring on the dry weight of the leaves of cassava (*Manihot esculenta*)

Distance from flaring point	Dry weight (g)		
	Leaf	Stem	Tubers
100m	1.12 ± 0.22	3.21 ± 0.64	2.01 ± 0.40
500m	2.81 ± 0.56	4.03 ± 0.81	3.21 ± 0.64
1000m	3.96 ± 0.79	5.28 ± 1.06	4.45 ± 0.89
Control	6.48 ± 1.30	10.14 ± 2.03	6.05 ± 1.21

Values are means of 5 replicates (±) standard error

Table 14: Effects of gas flaring on leaf production/plant in Yam (*Discorea* sp)

Distance from flaring point	Mean numbers of leaf/plant
100m	12.46 ± 2.49
500m	17.45 ± 3.49
1000m	20.01 ± 4.00
Control	26.60 ± 5.32

Values are means of 5 replicates (±) standard error

Table 15: Effects of gas flaring on leaf area development in (*Discorea* sp) Yam

Distance from flaring point	Mean numbers of leaf/plant
100m	27.28 ± 5.46
500m	52.57 ± 10.51
1000m	149.60 ± 29.92
Control	213.89 ± 42.78

Values are means of 5 replicates (±) standard error

Table 16: Effects of gas flaring on stem height in (*Dioscorea* sp) Yam

Distance from flaring point	Mean stem height (cm ²)
100m	33.45 ± 6.69
500m	87.62 ± 17.52
1000m	162.46 ± 32.49
Control	210.04 ± 42.01

Values are means of five (5) replicates (±) standard error

Table 17: Effects of gas flaring on fresh weight of the leaves, stem of Yam (*Dioscorea* sp)

Distance from flaring point	Mean Fresh weight (g)		
	Leaf	Stem	Tuber
100m	0.21 ± 0.06	1.50 ± 0.30	1.11 ± 0.22
500m	0.42 ± 0.08	1.73 ± 0.35	1.77 ± 0.35
1000m	1.06 ± 0.12	1.92 ± 0.38	3.42 ± 0.68
Control	3.06 ± 0.61	1.70 ± 0.54	4.67 ± 0.93

Table 18: Effects of gas flaring on dry weight of Yam (*Dioscorea* sp). Biomass (leaf, stems and tubers)

Distance from flaring point	Mean dry weight (g)		
	Leaf	Stem	Tuber
100m	0.11 ± 0.02	1.15 ± 0.23	1.10 ± 0.22
500m	0.21 ± 0.04	1.28 ± 0.26	1.41 ± 0.28
1000m	0.24 ± 0.05	1.33 ± 0.27	2.01 ± 0.40
Control	2.14 ± 0.43	2.00 ± 0.40	3.12 ± 0.62

Table 19: Effects of gas flaring on mean chlorophyll contents in the leaves of Yam, Cassava and Maize

Distances from flaring point	Yam leaves	Cassava leaves	Maize leaves
100m	22.40 ± 4.48	24.01 ± 4.80	23.28 ± 4.66
500m	37.26 ± 7.45	38.42 ± 7.68	38.41 ± 7.68
1000m	40.58 ± 8.12	48.62 ± 9.72	45.96 ± 9.19
Control	53.14 ± 10.63	54.12 ± 10.82	54.28 ± 10.86

Plate I: Morphological appearance of the plant in 100m from the flaring point

Plate II: Morphological appearance of plants (*Zea mays*, *Manihot esculenta* *Discorea* sp) in 500m from flaring point

Plate III: Morphological appearance of the plants in 1000m from flaring point

Plate IV: Control

CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

This research has attempted the assessment of the impact of petroleum gas flaring on three crop plants as at Amukpe – Sapele community, Delta State. Haven seen the dramatic effects of the gas flaring on the crops under investigation, it is thereby recommended that continuous cultivation of crops (Cassava, Yam and Maize) around the flaring points will lead to food shortage due to adverse effect on the plants as a result of the poisonous substance that are associated with the flare.

At present, the possibility of a permanent solution to these consequences ensuring from the continuous gas flaring activities seems very slight. However, responsiveness is a fundamental framework for its minimization, this will help in pushing to ameliorate management of the influences of the negative impacts of gas flaring on living and non living stress durability as well as appropriate diversities across the ecosystem.

Moreso, advance research on vegetation, climate change, climate – smart agriculture as well as ecosystem – based climate change mitigation prospects is vital. However researches on public health assessment on the contamination techniques should be undertaken regularly. Mitigating the cause and effects of gas flaring itself will be the best option.

Conclusively, investing on the practices to keep reducing the flaring of gas should be a top priority as the fight for food insecurity is on top gear. Gas flaring reduction plans may take years to get the results required, but now is the time to take the necessary action. Farmers that are specialized in the cultivation of Yam, Cassava and Maize are therefore advised to ensure that farms are situated in a considerable distances from gas flaring point. A distance of 2000 meters & above is recommended, haven seen that at 1000meters away there were still some significant effects on crops productivity.

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